

MXene multi-functionalization of Polyrotaxane based phase change materials and the applications in electronic devices thermal management

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Abstract. The aim of this work was to improve these limitations to increase the thermal conductivity and electromagnetic shielding of the leakage proof Phase change materials (PCMs) formed by a polyrotaxane that serves as a support material to encapsulate PEG 1k and PEG 6k, and MXene as multi-functional fillers. For this purpose, different contents of MXene were blended by using water as a solvent. The PCMs can be thermally processed conveniently by a hot press and the PEG 1k containing samples showed excellent flexibility. We conducted a systematic evaluation of the phase transition behavior of the material (latent heat, cycle stability, leakage, dimensional stability, thermal conductivity) and electromagnetic shielding performance tests. Notably, the PCMs created in this work achieve a high enthalpy values (123.9-159.6 J/g). The PCMs exhibited an increase of 44.3%, and 137.5% in thermal conductivity values with higher MXene content (5 wt%) for PLR-PEG6k and PLR-PEG1k, respectively, and show great shape stability and no leakage during phase change. The introduction of MXene can significantly improve the electromagnetic shielding performance of PCM composites. Typically, higher conductive samples (samples which contain MXene) offer a higher EMI SE shielding, reaching a maximum of 4.67 dB for 5.6 GHz for the most conductive sample, PLR-1K-MX5. These improvements solve the main problems of organic PEG based PCMs, thus making PLR-PEG-MXene-based PCMs a good candidate for use as thermal energy storage materials as thermoregulators of both solid-state disks and smart phone.

Keywords: Phase change materials, Thermal regulation, MXene, Polyrotaxane, Nanocomposites

1. Introduction

The 5G era is gradually approaching, with the introduction of high frequency, the upgrade of hardware components, and the exponential increase in the number of networked devices and antennas, electromagnetic interference between devices and within the device itself is ubiquitous, and electromagnetic interference and electromagnetic radiation are harmful to electronic devices. At the same time, with the updating and upgrading of electronic products, the power consumption of the equipment continues to increase, and the calorific value also rises rapidly. The bottleneck of high-frequency and high-power electronic products in the future is the electromagnetic radiation and generated heat. In order to solve these problems, more and more electromagnetic shielding and heat-treatment strategies were added to the design of electronic products. Therefore, the role of electromagnetic shielding and heat dissipation materials and devices will become more and more important, and the demand will continue to grow in the future.[1]

Among the thermal energy storage and thermal regulation materials, the phase change materials (PCM) stand out. These materials can store energy in the form of latent heat and release the energy when there is a difference in environmental temperature, this energy exchange occurs when there is a phase change of the material itself.[2] Within the many applications of PCM are: temperature adaptable greenhouses,[3] solar energy storage, [4]smartphone thermal regulation,[5] solar thermoelectric generator, [6] and so on. The main problems of PCMs in general, from their commercialization and production, are a low thermal conductivity, poor form stability, and PCM work substance leakage during the phase change that cause failures in the process. [7] Another main problem of PCMs is the difficulty of obtaining flexible phase change energy storage materials, because many of the prepared materials are rigid [8,9] or in powder form, which require secondary processing for practical applications.[10]

Within these organic PCMs, polyethylene glycol (PEG) based PCMs are widely used as energy storage materials in the fields of solar energy uses, [11] waste heat recovery, [12] and electric energy storage.[13] Among the properties of PEG are its large phase transformation enthalpy, wide transition temperature range, thermal and chemical stability, ease of chemical modification, good biocompatibility, and non-toxic

nature.[14] But like all organic PCMs, they have the same typical drawbacks, which are low thermal conductivity, and leakage during the phase change from solid to liquid. At present, the research on the modification and application of PEG anti-leakage and thermal conductivity is in-depth and extensive. [15,16] In our previous studies [10,17], PLR was an ideal support material for PEG, because it has the same main chain repeating structure.[18]

As mentioned before, smartphones continue to innovate and develop in the direction of thinner, lighter, integrated, and device miniaturized devices, and the arrival of the 5G era brings higher requirements for electromagnetic shielding and heat dissipation, and promotes the future process upgrade of electromagnetic shielding and heat conduction devices. The attenuation of electromagnetic shielding by electromagnetic shielding is mainly based on the principle of reflection and absorption of electromagnetic waves. Due to its excellent electrical conductivity, MXenes have recently gained increasing interest as highly efficient electromagnetic interference (EMI) and thermal management materials.[19] In fact, a typical EMI shielding material convert most of the EM radiation into heat dissipation,[20,21] which can produce considerable heat accumulation. Therefore, combined materials for EMI shielding and thermal management are getting increasing attention.[22] While MXene shows promising results, currently is most used as a functional filler which can increase the electrical conductivity, and thus, the EMI shielding efficiency. MXene is therefore employed as a functional filler for different polymer matrix materials such as PEG [20], PEG-based polyurethane [23] or paraffin wax[24].

To sum up, in order to obtain a phase change material with excellent processability, high thermal conductivity, high phase change enthalpy, stable shape and leakage-proof, and electromagnetic shielding effect. We will use PLR as the support materials, PEG1k (melting temperature is close to 30 °C) and PEG6k (with melting temperature about 60 °C) as the phase change work substance, and expect to prepare PCMs with tunable flexibility. The introduction of MXenes may take advantage of providing excellent multifunctional properties. The hydrophilicity of MXene itself will be beneficial to the ecofriendly mixing, compatibility and dispersion of materials to a certain extent. Generally speaking, the normal temperature

of the mobile phone is between 30-50 degrees when it is running. If it exceeds 50 degrees, it means that the mobile phone has started to heat up. If the heat cannot be exported in time, the frequency of the mobile phone will be reduced. Once the mobile phone heats up, it will not only affect the comfort of the user, but also have a relatively large negative impact on the performance of the mobile phone. Excessive heating will also cause damage to the hardware of the mobile phone, and what is even more likely to cause a fire when the mobile phone is charging. Therefore, it is very necessary to carry out heat dissipation treatment on mobile phones. Because the above-mentioned phase transition temperature should be 30~50 °C, it is more appropriate to choose PEG 1k (with melting temperature around 35 °C). In addition, the introduction of PEG1k is expected to realize flexible and leak-resistant PCMs. PEG 6k or other PEG with a higher melting point are widely used in battery heat management [25,26], light-to-heat energy conversion and storage [27], energy efficiency of buildings [28], efficient thermal management of electronic components,[29] and other applications. Therefore, this work will use PLR as the support material and MXene as the multifunctional filler to achieve excellent multifunctional PCMs with improved electromagnetic shielding and thermal conductivity.

2. Results and discussion

2.1. PCM preparation and structure investigation

Figure 1. (a) Two steps for fabrication of MXene from MAX-Ti₃AlC₂, (b) Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) morphology of the obtained MXene nano sheets, (c) chemical structure of polyrotaxane (as support materials), (d) the PCM sheet with large size (11 cm in length, 4 cm in width and 0.5 mm in thickness), (e) image of sample PLR-1k-MX5 to show the flexibility (curable), (f) sample PLR-6k-MX5 to show the re-mouldability (hot press from freeze dried foam), (g) filaments of sample PLR-1k-MX5 with diameter 4 mm, (h) pellets of sample PLR-1k-MX5 from the above filaments, (i) section morphology of PLR-1k, (j) section morphology of PLR-1k-MX5, (k) section morphology of PLR-6k, (l) section morphology of PLR-6k-MX5, (m) schematic of hydrogen bonding between PEG and MXene, (n) FTIR spectra showing transmittance (%) vs wavenumber (cm⁻¹) for PLR-6k, PLR-6k-MX5, PLR-1k, and PLR-1k-MX5.

(m) dispersion and interaction illustration of MXene in the PCM matrix, and (n) Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) curves of typical samples: PLR-1k, PLR-1k-MX5, PLR-6k, and PLR-6k-MX5.

The 2D layered MXene is synthesized through selectively etching the metal layers from the MAX precursor and newly incorporating some functional groups on the surfaces. [30] These terminating groups, such as O, OH, and/or F, provide MXene sheets with hydrophilic surface and good solubility in an aqueous solution, which greatly facilitate the incorporation with water-soluble PLR/PEG in the following mixing procedure to prepare the multifunctional PCM composites.[31]

In this work, the method for the preparation of MXenes **Figure 1(a)** is also detailed elsewhere [32,33]. The obtained SEM result of exfoliated MXene nanosheets are shown in **Figure 1b**. It's XRD curve is given in **Figure S1**. These results fully demonstrate the successful synthesis of MXenes. The obtained MXene were blended to PLR/PEG to fabricate the PCM composites. After PLR, PEG and MXene are mixed and dried, the sample can be hot-pressed easily and conveniently (**Figure 1f**). We can heat press anywhere between sheets and body shapes. The PLR-PEG1k relevant samples show excellent flexibility. Typically, the sample can be curled (**Figure 1e**). As shown in **Figure 1d**, large-area preparation can be achieved. In addition, PLR-1k-MX5, as a typical example, shows that it has extrusion filament (**Figure 1g**) and granulation (**Figure 1h**) properties, which also demonstrates the possibility of continuous processing manufacturing and 3D printing.

Figure 1i is the SEM curve of the comparison sample PLR-PEG1k. **Figure 1j** is the cross-section morphology of the sample PLR-1k-MX5. Both of them show a relatively rough cross section, indicating that the fracture of the material is ductile fracture. **Figure 1k** for sample PLR-6k shows the smooth brittle fracture morphology. The introduction of MXene shows some more cracks, which may be due to the spatial barrier of MXene nanosheets, inhibiting PEG from moving in a large range of space. On the other hand, MXene may induce the crystallization of PEG (its crystallinity is improved based on DSC calculations). In addition, for both PLR-1k-MX5 and PLR-6k-MX5, there are no significant MXene aggregation was found in the large field of view (**Figure S2**), and MXene can be tightly packed by the matrix, because no phase

separation interface detected. This shows that there is a good interfacial interaction between MXene and the matrix. We assign that this good dispersion is due to the surface multipolar functional groups of MXene, which ensure that MXene is easily dispersed in water and forms hydrogen bonds [19] with the matrix in PCM to obtain excellent dispersion, as illustrated in **Figure 1m**. FTIR data (Figure 1n) show that the introduction of MXene will weaken the hydrogen bond association to a certain extent, so the hydroxyl signal near 3400 cm^{-1} tends to be significantly weakened. The FTIR curves of all the samples refer to **Figure S4** and **S5**.

2.2. Phase change performances

Figure 2. (a) XRD curves of samples PLR-1k, PLR-1k-MX5, PLR-6k and PLR-6k-MX5, (b) Intuitive characterization of the anti-leakage performance and shape stability of the samples, (c) Melting enthalpy values and solidification values of PLR-PEG 1k system, (d) Melting enthalpy values and solidification values of PLR-PEG 6k system, (e) parameters of sample PLR-1k-MX5 for cycling stability, (f) parameters of sample PLR-6k-MX5 for cycling stability, (g) thermal conductivity results of PLR-PEG1k system, and (h) thermal conductivity results of PLR-PEG6k system.

The XRD curves of the typical samples are shown in **Figure 2a**. The peak at $2\theta \sim 9.8^\circ$ corresponds to the crystalline (002) plane of MXene. The peak at 12.7° (110) obtained from the PLR crystal consisting of α -CD and PEG. [34] The peaks at $\sim 19^\circ$ and $\sim 23^\circ$ are the crystal plane (120), (112)/(032) respectively, of PEG. The results showed that PLR/PEG (both 1k and 6k) maintained good crystallization ability with the introduction of MXene. This is also a prerequisite for the energy storage during phase change. In addition, the presence of PLR crystallization peaks ((002) plane) indicates the presence of physical crosslinking points for cyclodextrin with PEO chain crystallization, which is an important reason for ensuring the excellent shape stability of the material, because the melting temperature is higher than 90°C . [17]

PLR has been proven to be an excellent phase change material [10] and an excellent carrier for PEG work substance. With the introduction of MXene in this study, the obtained sample still maintains excellent shape stability and anti-leakage properties. As shown in Figure 2b, no significant dimensional changes or leakage occurred in the material after heat treatment at 70°C for 2 h (on filter paper). We continue to conduct DSC testing on the samples to collect their typical phase change performance parameters. The specific test curves are given in **Figure S6-S15**. **Figure 2c** and **d** show the latent heat of phase change (ΔH_m) and crystallization enthalpy (ΔH_s). For the PEG 1k relevant samples, both ΔH_s and ΔH_m showed a downward tendency after the introduction of MXene. Fortunately, the latent heat of fusion can still be maintained at 123.9 J/g at 5% MXene. For the PEG 6k system, the terminal effect of PEG is lower and the crystallization ability is enhanced to a certain extent. The introduction of MXene will act as a crystallization-induced nucleation agent, hence the enthalpy increase that occurs at low MXene loading (for

both sample PLR-6k-MX1 and PLR-6k-MX3). When the MXene content increases to 5 wt%, the impurity effect of the fillers dominates and the enthalpy value decreases. But it can still maintain a high level of 145.4 J/g for PLR-6k-MX5. Cycling stability (Both PLR-1k-MX5 and PLR-6k-MX5) was performed for 80 cycles. It can be seen that core indicators such as ΔH_m and ΔH_s remain relatively stable (**Figure 2e, f**), which shows that the material has good cycle stability. The specific parameter indicators are given in **Table S3, 4**.

Furthermore, **Figure 2g** and **h** show the TC index of the samples. The TC increased with the increasing of MXene contents for both PEG 1k and PEG 6k relevant samples. Specifically, when 5% of MXene is added, the PLR-1k relevant samples can increase from 0.2953 W/(m·K) to 0.7013 W/(m·K) (with an increase of 137.5%); while the PLR-6k system can increase from 0.3348 W/(m·K) to 0.4833 W/(m·K) (with an increase of 44.3%). As it further can be seen in **Figure 2g, h**, the PEG1k relevant sample has a higher increasing slope (7.788) than that of PEG 6k relevant samples (with value of 2.680). The possible reason is that MXene forms a better network structure in the PEG 1k system and acts as a thermally conductive framework, which will be further discussed in section 2.4. Some evidence can be obtained from the image after TGA and fire test. On the other hand, it can be seen from SEM that PEG6k is spatially limited by 2D MXene, and its crystallinity is quite high relative to that of PEG 1k, so some void defects were generated during the cooling process (**Figure S3**).

2.3. Electrical conductivity and electromagnetic shielding

Figure 3. (a) Electrical conductivity of PLR/PEG/MXene composites upon loading, (b) EMI SE of the different samples of thickness 1.5 mm, (c) shielding measurement test scheme, (d) schematic representation of the mechanism of EMI shielding of the PLR/PEG/Mxene composites, (e) specific shielding effectiveness (SSE) and (f) shielding efficiency (SE).

EMI shielding is related with the electrical conductivity of the composites. Therefore, DC electrical conductivity is presented in **Figure 3(a)**. Among the different PLR-PEG-MXene composites, it is observed that PEG 1k containing composites present a higher conductivity than PEG 6k containing composites. Regarding MXene loading, conductivity increases, as expected, with higher MXene content [35]. In fact, the maximum conductivity is reached for PLR-1k-MX5 with $3.23 \cdot 10^{-6}$ S/m, compared to $1.36 \cdot 10^{-7}$ S/m of PEG 1k, in agreement with other report. [36]

To determine the EMI shielding mechanism the samples, EMI SE was measured and is presented in **Figure 3b** between the range of 1.8-6.0 GHz. The schematics of the experimental setup are shown in

Figure 3c. The results are in clear agreement with the conductivity results: higher conductive samples (samples which contain MXene) offer a higher EMI SE shielding, reaching a maximum of 4.67 dB for 5.6 GHz for the most conductive sample, PLR-1k-MX5. These results are in accordance with previous reports. [20]. It has also been found that the total value of EMI shielding effectiveness in other reinforced polymers, with a constant MXene ratio, increases slightly with increasing frequency (Figure 3 (b)), which is also in agreement with previous findings mentioned in previous reports.[37]

For far-field (**Figure 3b**), it can be concluded that increasing the percentage of MXene generates an increase in the attenuation of the transmitted signal, but it is also observed that a higher MXene content generates a higher shielding, which is due to the fact that this usually results in a higher polymeric conductivity by reducing the mean free volume of the polymer. [38] It is interesting to note that the origin of the shielding, both in the near and far field, is caused by interface polarisation, defective polarisation and surface functional group polarisation. [39,40] which explains why PLR-1K despite having a higher conductivity shows lower EMI shielding than PLR-6K-MX5. With respect to the near-field tests, PLR-PEG/Mxene, as shown in the results (**Figure S16** and S17), can be useful for applications where it is desired to shield the electric fields completely and let the magnetic field pass through. Another application of great interest would be to take advantage of the interaction with the nearby electric fields, to generate photothermal conversion of the same, so that by harnessing this heat energy is generated. [41]

A possible mechanism of the EMI shielding is depicted in **Figure 3d**, where the incident electromagnetic waves interact with the PLR-PEG-MXene composite, being partially reflected and partially absorbed by the sample. Due to the presence of local currents of the MXene, the incoming EM waves interact with the high-density electron carriers, which leads to massive ohmic losses and thus, attenuation of the EM wave [19]. Also, due to the reflections between multiple MXene nanosheets, the dissipation of the EM is promoted. This is the reason why higher loading implies higher EMI shielding. Nonetheless, part of the EMI radiation can pass through the sample, while due to the higher MXene content, as observed, lower EM waves can pass through. Figure 3(d), shows the configuration employed to perform these measurements.

The specific shielding effectiveness (SSE) and the shielding efficiency are depicted also in Figure 3 (e) and (f) for two representative frequencies at two wave bands, 2.4 GHz (S-band) and 5.6 GHz (C-Band), The latter parameter takes into consideration the density and the thickness of the samples, showing that the denser samples (those with PEG1k and MXene) show a higher SSE, even without the addition of MXene, which should be taken into consideration for low-weight applications.

2.4 Thermal stability and fire behaviors

Figure 4. (a) Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) curves of PEG1k relevant PCM composites, (b) TGA curves of PEG 6k relevant PCM composites, (c) fire behaviors of sample PLR-1k, (d) fire behaviors of sample PLR-1k-MX5, (e) fire behaviors of sample PLR-6k, and (f) fire behaviors of sample PLR-6k-MX5.

As shown in **Figure 4a-b**, we found that the introduction of MXene will catalyze the early decomposition of cyclodextrin, as shown in the red rectangle regions in both Figure 4a and b, which directly manifests as the forward shift of the first step. Fortunately, all samples began to decompose above 250 °C, which fully ensures that the material is stable within the normal thermal management application temperature range. We further conducted direct ignition experiments on samples PLR-1k, PLR-1k-MX5, PLR-6k and PLR-6k-MX5, and their pictures are shown in **Figure 4c-d**. We discover the layered MXene endowed PLR-PEG film with remarkable anti-dripping performance (Figure 4c and 4e), and the layer structure of composite film remained during the whole combustion process (shown in Figure 4d and 4f). The protective barrier of MXene can effectively blocked the transfer of heat/oxygen and then prevented the appearance of melt drip.

The decorated MXene layer significantly accelerated the decomposition of CD, and the residual content at 800 °C was improved by three times higher than neat PLR-PEG. More importantly, the complete shape and structure of the textile can be maintained even after burning test (Figure 4b inset). The compact and well-distributed MXene nanosheets acted as the effective flame retardant on the PLR-PEG, (which is also proved in the previous reports [31] and significantly enhanced the anti-dripping performance during the whole combustion process.

2.5. Application cases

2.5.1 Thermal regulations of smart phone by using flexible PLR-PEG1k relevant PCMs

Figure 5a shows a schematic diagram of the test process of PCM's thermal management during the use of a smartphone. Considering the practical necessity of saving materials, our main coverage area is the CPU core area, which corresponds to the upper half of the mobile phone. It is divided into three temperature regions of specific concern, namely region A, B and C. The temperature changes during the use of WeChat video calls. Because the development trend of smart devices is also flexible, wearable and intelligent, we choose flexible PCM sample to prepare functional patches with a thickness of about 0.5 mm by hot press. The screenshot of the infrared imaging process of its specific test is shown in **Figure 5b**. It can be compared

with the reference sample (the test curves or images without PCM) that the temperature adjustment change is also obvious. Especially at $t=3000$ s, the CPU area temperature has a significant difference among the reference sample and the PCM containing samples. Based on the temperature changes in each temperature region, the specific temperature-time curves were derived. First, region A, which is the CPU area, is the initial heat source for investigation. Its thermal response is almost determined by the phase transition process because the sample thickness is low and is close to the core heat source.

It can be found that compared with reference, all samples containing PCM have a significant effect of regulating temperature, and more MXene can ensure better thermal management capacity, especially for region A. It is worth pointing out that sample PLR-1k-MX5 can decrease 4.3 °C of the reference temperature of region A. For region B, the heat source mainly comes from the absorption from region A, mainly because they are quite close. Therefore, its temperature change tendency is similar to that of region A. For region C, the heat source comes from the thermal diffusion of the mobile phone itself, and also from the heat conduction of the phase change material. Since the temperature in Region C of cellphone is relatively low (comparing to Region A and B), its heat source is not only the one generated by the mobile phone, but also the heat transfer from Region A and B of the PCM sheet. A combination of factors results in a sample with high thermal conductivity having a high temperature at the same time (Figure 5e). We can understand that for low thermal conductivity, PCM with high enthalpy value is conducive to the regulation of heat absorption and cooling. If PCM also has high thermal conductivity, it can also have the effect of equalizing heat. Because PLR-1k-MX5 has the highest thermal conductivity, its temperature increase in the middle and late stages significantly exceeds that of several other samples (**Figure 5e** and f). It can be seen that the heating process of the overall components has a relatively long period of stability in the later stage. This is mainly because the heat absorption and heat dissipation of the material (through conduction and diffusion in the surrounding materials like air transmission) form a balance within a certain period of time.

Figure 5. (a) Phone with PCM and the temperature regulation illustration, (b) IR images of the samples: empty cellphone, PLR-1k, PLR-1k-MX1, PLR-1k-MX3 and PLR-1k-MX5, (c) temperature change curves of region A, (d) temperature change curves of region B and (e) temperature change curves of region C.

2.5.2 Solid State Disk (SSD) heat management

A typical application of PCMs is the thermal management of electronic devices. As shown in **Figure 6a**, phase change materials usually work with metal heatsink to regulate the temperature of solid state disk (SSD). As shown in **Figure 6b**, the insulation layer, protecting sheet (Polypropylene (PP) with 2 mm in thickness), PCM (70 mm×22 mm×1 mm in thickness, which is the same as the size of commercial product) and the metal heatsink stacked together from the bottom to the top. **Figure 6c** shows the schematic diagram and a top view photograph of two schematic devices with PCM of the whole material test system. **Figure**

6d shows the IR images of different samples at different heating time. We can further obtain the measured temperature change heating curves, as shown in Figure 6e-f.

Figure 6. (a) Solid state disk (SSD) and the image of SSD with heat sink; (b) Layered structure of simulated device; (c) the testing illustration and the images of the devices; (d) IR images of typical samples: the device without PCM and with PLR-6k-MX5; (e) the heating curves of the PCM in current work and some typical commercial samples; and (f) heating curves of the protecting sheet without PCM and with PCMs.

As shown in **Figure 6e** and **f**, the state of the device can reach a relatively stable equilibrium state after heating for 750 s. During the whole heating cycle, sample PLR-6k and PLR-6k-MX5 in this study showed significantly better temperature control capacity than both the reference sample and commodities (3M and JOSBO as examples). Specifically, the temperature of the protecting part with PCM was significantly lower than that of blank sample (76.9 °C at t=3000 s) and commercial PCMs (74.8 °C at t=3000 s for 3M, 75.8 °C at t=3000 s for JOSBP). The DSC curves of the commercial PCMs are given in **Figure S26** and **S27**. It can be found that the latent heat values of both commercial PCM are very low (2-4 J/g). Therefore, its thermal control mainly depends on its heat conduction to the heat sink to achieve heat dissipation. Although its thermal conductivity is generally higher than 1.5 W/(m·K). However, the results of this study show that under a certain time scale, the phase change enthalpy plays a significant role in the thermal management of electronic devices. In this study, the significant existence of temperature difference for a long time fully proves the significant utility of PCM. At the same time, it also shows the practical significance of PCM in the field of thermal control of electronic devices. Typically, the specimen with PLR-6k-MX5 shows a decreasing of 7.9 °C relative to the reference test. We expect that under the premise of maintaining high latent heat, and then further improve the thermal conductivity of the material, it is expected that more significant heat management effect will be achieved.

3. Conclusion

PLR/PEG/MXene nanocomposites with different PEG molecular weight (PEG 1k and PEG 6k) and various contents of MXene (1%, 3% and 5 wt%) were successfully prepared by using water as the solvent. The addition of MXene to PLR/PEG maintained shape stability and the heat storage capacities during phase transition. A great thermal performance was observed, obtaining high latent heat values (123.9-130.9 J/g for PLR-PEG 1k-MXene and 145.4-159.6 J/g for PLR-PEG 6k-MXene) and cycle stability. The MXene contributed a significant increase of thermal conductivity with 44.3 % for PLR-1k-MX5, and 137.5% for PLR-6k-MX5, comparing to PLR-PEG in thermal conductivity, and this increase was linear with increasing MXene content. The introduction of MXene can significantly improve the electromagnetic shielding

performance of PCM composites. Typically, samples which contain MXene offer a higher EMI SE shielding, reaching a maximum of 4.67 dB for 5.6 GHz for the most conductive sample, PLR-1K-MX5. The introduction of MXene has a significant promotion effect on TGA carbon residue. There is no droplet formation during the combustion process. This shows to a certain extent that MXene has a certain flame retardant function for the PLR-PEG phase change system. The application cases showed obvious heat regulation for both smartphone and SSD. To summarize, the high thermal performance with high enthalpy values and high thermal conductivity values added the great form stability that we obtained in PLR/PEG MXene; thus, its simple fabrication process and multi-functionalization make it an optimal PCM for use as a latent heat thermal energy storage material in practical applications.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Guang-Zhong Yin: Conceptualization, Methodology, Data curation, Writing-original draft, Writing-review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Alba Marta López:** Data curation, Methodology, Writing-review & editing. **Ignacio Collado:** Data curation, Writing-original draft, Writing-review & editing. **Antonio Vázquez-López:** Data curation, Writing-original draft, Writing-review & editing. **Xiang Ao:** Data curation, Writing-review & editing. **Jose Hobson:** Data curation, Writing-review & editing. **Silvia G. Prolongo:** Data curation, Writing-review & editing. **De-Yi Wang:** Methodology, Writing-review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

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